

Review of the spiders (Arachnida: Araneae) as prey of the mud-dauber wasps in Gauteng and Limpopo

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ABSTRACT: Spiders are preyed on by a wide variety of creatures, such as mud-dauber wasps of the family Sphecidae. They are named after the multi-chambered nests they construct of mud or clay. Mud nests serve as brooding rooms for their larvae. From eight wasp nests, a total of 219 spiders were sampled, and the average per nest varied from 10 to 44. The Araneidae was most sampled (48.4%), followed by the Thomisidae (25.1%), Oxyopidae (13.2%) and Salticidae (5.9%). *Neoscona subfusca* (38.8%) was the species most preyed on. A greater number of immature individuals (70.1%) were collected compared to adults.

Keywords: Araneidae, Oxyopidae, Salticidae, Sphecidae, Thomisidae, predation

INTRODUCTION

Spiders are preyed upon by various creatures, including insects, arachnids, nematodes, reptiles, birds, and vertebrates, as well as fungi, parasitic nematodes, and mites. The southern African sub-region has at least four families of wasps known to parasitise spiders. The Eurytomidae and Ichneumonidae parasitise spider egg sacs, while the Pompilidae are known as the spider-hunting wasps, and Sphecidae are known as the mud-dauber and water-carrier wasps. In the Sphecidae family, the *Sceliphron spirifex* (Linnaeus, 1758) is known as a mud-dauber wasp and *Chalybion tibiale* (Fabricius, 1781) and *Chalybion spinolae* (Lepeletier, 1845), both water-carrier wasps. *Chalybion* species excavate cells within vertical structures, such as earth banks, and modify pre-existing cavities, whereas *Sceliphron* species build free, aerial mud cells (Gess et al., 1982). Both genera are exclusively spider hunters (Coville, 1987). In the Western Cape, *C. spinolae* has been documented by Nel et al. (2014), that they preyed only on two theridiid spider species, *Latrodectus indistinctus* (Cambridge, 1904) and *L. geometricus* (Koch, 1841). Their observations spanned 5 years and involved approximately 200 wasp nests.

Sceliphron spirifex is the species known to prey on spiders in Africa (Jocqué, 1988). It is medium-sized, 17–27 mm long, with a dull black colour and a long, yellow petiole (waist). The legs are black with yellow bands, and the wings are transparent. These wasps are solitary, not aggressive, and do not sting unless mishandled. The females are larger than the males and have a visible sting. They inhabit diverse habitats across Africa and Southern Europe but are strongly associated with buildings and other human-made structures. The wasps employ paralytic venom to immobilise spiders. The venom causes paralysis of the spider's skeletal neuromuscular systems that may be temporary or prolonged, but it does not affect the heart or circulatory system.

Mud-dauber wasps are named after the multi-chambered nests they construct of mud or clay. They are solitary wasps, and their nests are frequently built in sheltered places, often in or around houses. The female wasp collects mud, rolls it into a ball and carries it to the nest. At the nest, it is moulded into place with the wasp's mandibles. After completing the mud nest, the female captures spiders (or insects) to fill the cells. The spider is stung and paralysed before being placed in the nest. A single egg is deposited on the spider's abdomen within each cell, which is then sealed with mud. After the wasp has finished a series of cells, she departs and does not return. The larvae that hatch from the eggs feed on the living tissue of the paralysed spiders. New adult wasps emerge to start the process over again. Only the larvae feed on spiders or insects, while the adult female wasp survives on plant juices.

Figure 2. Spiders removed from a mud nest from Modimolle
Credit: Marita Beneke.

Figures 1. Mud dauber nest. Credit: J.M. Kriek

Figure 3. Specimens from a mud dauber mud nest 3 scanned by J.M. Kriek

METHOD

Six wasp nests were dissected at the ARC -Spider Research Centre they were collected by J.M. Kriek and personnel at ARC-PPRI.

TABLE 1. The spider species removed from eight mud dauber nests with the guild (G) they occupy WD Web dweller; PD Plant dweller.

FAMILIES	LOCALITY/SPECIES	G	SEX	TOT
NEST 1 PRETORIA: RIETONDALE RESEACH STATION n=44				
Araneidae	<i>Neoscona triangula</i>	WD	1 m	1
Oxyopidae	<i>Oxyopes vanderysti</i>	PD	9m; 3f; 1imm	13
Philodromidae	<i>Philodromus guineensis</i>	PD	1 imm	1
Thomisidae	<i>Misumenops rubrodecoratus</i>	PD	1 f	1
Thomisidae	<i>Synema langheldi</i>	PD	15 f; 1 imm	16
Thomisidae	<i>Thomisus citrinellus</i>	PD	1 f; 1 imm	2
Thomisidae	<i>Thomisus scrupeus</i>	PD	2 m; 6 imm	8
Thomisidae	<i>Tmarus cameliformis</i>	PD	1 f; 1 m	2
NEST 2 PRETORIA: RIETONDALE n=10				
Thomisidae	<i>Oxytate argenteooculata</i>	PD	10 imm	10
NEST 3 PRETORIA: COLBYN n=38				
Araneidae	<i>Neoscona blondeli</i>	WD	1 imm	1
Araneidae	<i>Neoscona subfusca</i>	WD	22imm	22
Oxyopidae	<i>Oxyopes bothai</i>	PD	8 imm	8
Philodromidae	<i>Philodromus guineensis</i>	PD	5 imm	5
Salticidae	<i>Heliophanus</i> sp.	PD	1 imm	1
Salticidae	<i>Thyene natalii</i>	PD	1 f	1
NEST 4 PRETORIA: PRETORIA NORTH				
Araneidae	<i>Neoscona subfusca</i>	WD	1 imm	1
Salticidae	<i>Heliophanus</i> sp.	PD	1 imm	1
Salticidae	<i>Thyene natalii</i>	PD	1 imm	1
Thomisidae	<i>Thomisus scrupeus</i>	PD	2 m	2
Thomisidae	<i>Tmarus cameliformis</i>	PD	4 imm	4
Uloboridae	<i>Uloborus plumipes</i>	WD	2 f; 2 imm	4
NEST 5 CENTURION: IRENE n=28				
Araneidae	<i>Neoscona subfusca</i>	WD	6 f; 4 imm	10
Araneidae	<i>Nemoscolus</i> sp.	WD	3 f	3
Araneidae	<i>Pararaneus cyrtoscapus</i>	WD	7 imm	7
Araneidae	<i>Trichonephila fenestrata</i>	WD	2 imm	2
Philodromidae	<i>Philodromus guineensis</i>	PD	1 f; 1 imm	2
Salticidae	<i>Hyllus brevitarsis</i>	PD	4 imm	4
NEST 6 CENTURION: ELDORADO PARK				
Araneidae	<i>Neoscona subfusca</i>	WD	6 f; 23 imm	29
Araneidae	<i>Pararaneus cyrtoscapus</i>	WD	3 imm	3
Philodromidae	<i>Philodromus guineensis</i>	PD	1 f; 1 imm	2
Oxyopidae	<i>Hamataliwa rostrifrons</i>	PD	4 imm	4
Oxyopidae	<i>Peucetia transvaalica</i>	PD	1 imm	1
NEST 7 MODIMOLE n=27 Fig. 2				
Araneidae	<i>Araneus apricus</i>	WD	1 imm	1
Araneidae	<i>Neoscona blondeli</i>	WD	2 imm	2
Araneidae	<i>Neoscona subfusca</i>	WD	20 imm	20
Oxyopidae	<i>Oxyopes bothai</i>	PD	1 f	1
Thomisidae	<i>Tmarus cameliformis</i>	PD	1 f	1
Salticidae	<i>Belippo meridionalis</i>	PD	1 imm	1
Salticidae	<i>Hyllus dotatus</i>	PD	1 imm	1
NEST 8 CENTURION n=20 Fig. 4				
Araneidae	<i>Araneus apricus</i>	WD	1 imm	1
Araneidae	<i>Neoscona subfusca</i>	WD	3 imm	3
Cheiracanthiidae	<i>Cheiramiona</i> sp.	PD	1 imm	1
Oxyopidae	<i>Oxyopes</i> sp. 3 (green)	PD	2 imm	2
Philodromidae	<i>Philodromus guineensis</i>	PD	1 imm	1
Salticidae	<i>Heliophanus</i> sp.	PD	3 imm	3
Thomisidae	<i>Ansiea tuckeri</i>	PD	1 m	1
Thomisidae	<i>Synema diana</i>	PD	5f; 2 imm	7
Thomisidae	<i>Tmarus cameliformis</i>	PD	1f	27

Figure 4. Specimens from a mud dauber mud nest 8.

TABLE 2. The spider families sampled from mud-dauber wasps nests.

FAMILIES	TOT	%
Araneidae	106	48.4
Cheiracanthiidae	1	0.5
Oxyopidae	29	13.2
Philodromidae	11	5.0
Salticidae	13	5.9
Thomisidae	55	25.1
Uloboridae	4	1.8
	219	

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Two hundred nineteen spiders were sampled from eight wasp nests (Table 1). The total number of spiders per nest varied from 10 to 44. The Araneidae (n=106) was the spider family most sampled (48.4%), followed by the Thomisidae (25.1%) and Araneidae (13.2%) (Table 2). Of all the species samples, *Neoscona subfusca*, with 85 specimens (38.8%), was the most frequently encountered. More immature spiders were collected (67.4%) compared to adults (males 7.2% and females 25.4%).

Jocqué (1988) reported on the prey of 40 mud-dauber wasp nests in Central Africa. Of the 598 specimens sampled, the Araneidae were also the most common prey (56%), followed by Salticidae (30.7%) and Thomisidae (7.9%). Both studies show that the wasps specialise on spiders of the shrub and tree layer, as no ground dwellers were sampled. This contrasts with a collection from Sierra Leone where ground dwellers like Lycosidae and Zodariidae were also preyed on (White, 1962). In Central Africa, more web dwellers (57.4 %) fell prey to the wasp, compared to this study, where only 48.3% were web dwellers.

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